

Cardiovascular Autonomic Reactivity in Patients with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome

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Abstract:

Background: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a multisystemic disorder characterized by endocrine, metabolic, and reproductive system abnormalities. The diagnostic criteria include chronic anovulation and hyperandrogenism. The autonomic nervous system plays a role in pathogenesis. Women with PCOS often experience conditions like oscillatory sleep apnea, hypertension, depression, obesity, and type 2 diabetes linked to an autonomic nervous system imbalance.

Objectives: The aim and objective of this study are to evaluate the use of cardiovascular reflex testing in patients with PCOS and in healthy controls.

Material and Methods: Out of 60 individuals, 30 of whom were diagnosed with PCOS, and 30 healthy controls, we conducted autonomic function tests, including handgrip tests, cold pressor tests, deep breathing tests (DBT), lying-to-stand assessments (LST), and the Valsalva maneuver. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS edition 21, with Mann-Whitney and unpaired t-tests used for normal and atypical distributions of parameters. The study aimed to identify potential health issues.

Results: The study found that PCOS patients had a significantly lower ($p = 0.00^*$) delta HR (DBT) and E:I ratio (DBT) compared to healthy individuals. In PCOS patients, the Valsalva ratio was significantly lower ($p = 0.00^*$). The 30:15 ratio decreased significantly ($p = 0.00^*$) in PCOS patients compared to the healthy control group. PCOS patients had a higher heart rate (LST) than the control group ($p = 0.00^*$). The cold pressor test showed statistical significance in PCOS patients ($p = 0.00^*$), while the handgrip test was statistically insignificant.

Conclusions: The increasing prevalence of PCOS, along with obesity and hypertension, increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. Therapeutic modalities may adversely affect the cardiovascular system, highlighting the need for ways to reduce these risks. Cardiovascular reflex test can be used to assess cardiac autonomic function in PCOS patients.

Keywords: PCOS, Autonomic Dysfunction, Cardiovascular Reflex, Cardiovascular Autonomic Reactivity, Sympathetic Tone, Parasympathetic Tone.

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Introduction

The Rotterdam Criteria identifies PCOS, a reproductive disorder affecting 5–10% of the global population, with clinical signs including irregular menstrual cycles, hyperandrogenism, numerous ovarian cysts, hirsutism, acne, male pattern alopecia, and infertility. [1]. Comorbidities like obesity, insulin resistance, and type 2 diabetes are strongly related to PCOS, with androgenic over activity

being a key predictor of cardiovascular problems. Obesity is common in the PCOS-affected population. [2]. Obesity is a common association with PCOS, affecting half of affected populations, and a significant risk factor for cardiometabolic illnesses, though evidence is limited to determining independent connections. [3,4]. PCOS is linked to hyperinsulinemia, high blood pressure, dyslipidemia,

metabolic syndrome, and sleep apnea, affecting cardiac autonomic function and increasing the risk of various health conditions. [5]. According to research, women with PCOS display greater sympathetic nervous system activity and lower parasympathetic (vagal) function. [6]

Autonomic dysfunction has a significant correlation with cardiovascular mortality and is linked to metabolic and cardiovascular disorders. [7, 8] Heart rate turbulence (HRT) and heart rate variability (autonomic functions) provide important information about the cardiac autonomic system's function. [9] Autonomic functions quantify both the variations in heart rate between consecutive heartbeats and the variations within each individual heartbeat cycle. [10] Reduced autonomic functions have been shown in earlier research to be a predictor of increased cardiac death. HRT (Heart Rate Turbulence) refers to a variation in the length of the sinus rhythm cycle that occurs after isolated premature ventricular beats (VPB). This method has been deemed appropriate for predicting the outcome of heart failure and other diseases, as well as estimating the risk after a heart attack. [11,12] Autonomic functions and baroreflex sensitivity (BRS) are critical for assessing autonomic control. It's recommended to use cardiovascular reflex tests instead of BRS in PCOS patients, as autonomic dysfunction in PCOS is characterized by decreased heart rate variability signifying autonomic dysfunctions and an exaggerated blood pressure response to exercise. [13,14]

This study aims to assess autonomic reactivity in PCOS patients due to insufficient research on cardiovascular reflex tests in Indian patients. The purpose of this study is to assess PCOS patients' cardiac autonomic reactivity.

Material and Methods

At Ganesh Shankar Vidyarthi Memorial Medical College in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India, and the Department of Physiology collaborated with the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology to design and carry out a cross-sectional study involving 60 patients. Thirty age-matched control female participants without PCOS symptoms and thirty PCOS-positive female participants (based on the Rotterdam Criteria) were included in the study.

The measurement of waist circumference was taken up to the umbilicus on the abdomen. The measurement of hip circumference was taken at the hips' largest circumference. A wall-mounted stadiometer and a spring balance were used to measure the subjects' weight and height, respectively. Body mass index (BMI) and waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) were computed, and participants were categorized using the Asian BMI criterion. Following a five-minute rest period, the baseline heart rate (HR) was determined. Using a mercury sphygmomanometer, base-

line measurements of systolic and diastolic blood pressure (SBP) and DBP were made, followed by a five-minute rest period. Utilizing the modified Ferriman-Gallwey score, hirsutism was assessed.

We performed autonomic function tests during the follicular phase of the menstrual cycle, specifically during the amenorrhoeic period, to avoid the effects of ovulatory hormones. Before the study began, participants in both groups were instructed to abstain from alcohol and caffeinated beverages for 12 hours and too fast for at least 4 hours. [15]

Cardiovascular reflex tests were performed evaluate both parasympathetic and sympathetic reactivity.

Testing for parasympathetic reactivity

Test of Deep Breathing: Following a five-minute rest period, participants were instructed to gently breathe in and out at a rate of six breaths per minute, while an ongoing ECG recording was made throughout this deep breathing exercise. Next, the ratio of expiration to inspiration (E:I) was computed. The E:I ratio is the average of the minimum and maximum RR intervals during inhalation and exhalation.

The Valsalva Manoeuvre: A mouthpiece connected to a sphygmomanometer was used by the participants to forcefully exhale, and they were instructed to hold their expiratory pressure at 40 mmHg for 15 seconds. Lead II's ECG was captured for a minute, both when the subject relaxed and exhaled forcefully. The ratio of the longest RR interval in Phase IV to the shortest RR interval in Phase II was used to compute the Valsalva ratio (VR).

Standing vs. Lying (30:15 ratio): This test measured the variations in heart rate between a supine and standing position. Following a five-minute rest period, participants used a passive tilt table to tilt 60 degrees, and they remained in that position for an additional five minutes.

The ratio of the longest RR interval, which occurs on the 30th beat after standing, to the shortest RR interval, which occurs around the 15th beat, is known as the 30:15 ratio.

Test of Isometric Handgrip: A mercury sphygmomanometer was used to record baseline blood pressure following a five-minute rest period. To obtain the maximum voluntary contraction, participants were instructed to hold the hand grip dynamometer with their dominant hand and full force for a few seconds. The maximum force exerted was then recorded. The next task given to the participants was to press the dynamometer at 30% of their maximum voluntary contraction for four minutes. At one minute, two minutes, and four minutes, additional blood pressure readings were recorded. A baseline recording of Δ DBP was made.

Test for cold pressure: Initial After a five-minute break, blood pressure was measured with a mercury sphygmomanometer. Next, participants were instructed to submerge their non-dominant hand for a minute in cold water (4-6 oC). At one minute, one and a half minutes, and four minutes, blood pressure was recorded. A baseline recording of Δ DBP was made.

From lying to standing: This exam assesses both parasympathetic and sympathetic nervous system activity. Δ SBP was measured while lying down and at the passive tilt to measure sympathetic activity. At thirty, one, two, and five minutes, blood pressure was recorded.

The statistical analysis: This study's data administration, analysis, and interpretation were all carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 21.0. The researchers presented their findings after collecting data from the control and chronic PCOS groups using descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations (SD). To see if there were any statistically significant differences between the groups, the researchers used an unpaired t-test.

The study used a p-value of less than 0.05 to determine statistical significance.

Results

This study included sixty participants, including PCOS patients as well as healthy controls. PCOS patients had an average age of 34.23 ± 4.56 years, whereas the healthy population's average age was 32.12 ± 3.84 years. Table 1 shows that the mean BMI of the PCOS group was 24.32 ± 1.17 , while the control group's BMI was 23.88 ± 1.32 . PCOS patients' average heart rate (HR) was 84.67 ± 5.01 bpm, whereas healthy people's HR was 83.49 ± 3.69 beats per minute (bpm).

According to Table 2, the delta HR (DBT) of PCOS patients was 13.23 ± 1.34 , while the DBT of healthy people was 15.11 ± 1.19 ($p = 0.000^*$). The E:I ratio (DBT) for PCOS patients was 1.18 ± 0.49 , whereas the ratio for healthy people was 1.31 ± 0.21 ($p = 0.000^*$). Table 2 shows that the Valsalva ratio was 1.42 ± 0.65 in healthy individuals and 1.18 ± 0.78 in PCOS patients ($p = 0.000^*$). The PCOS patients demonstrated a significant decrease in the 30:15 ratio and a decline in systolic blood pressure (LST) ($p = 0.00^*$) in comparison to the healthy control group.

Heart rate (LST) increased significantly more in PCOS patients (13.41 ± 3.71) than in the control group (8.55 ± 5.28 ; $p = 0.000^*$). Based on a comparison between the PCOS patients and the control group, the cold pressor test results showed statistical significance ($p = 0.087^*$). The handgrip test's statistically insignificant ($p=0.090$) results are shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Comparison of basal parameters in chronic PCOS and healthy controls

	PCOS (Mean \pm SD)	Healthy Controls (Mean \pm SD)	p Value
Age (years)	34.23 ± 4.56	32.12 ± 3.84	-
BMI	24.32 ± 1.17	23.88 ± 1.32	0.946
Mean Heart Rate (bpm)	84.67 ± 5.01	83.49 ± 3.69	1.098
Systolic BP (mmHg)	122.84 ± 7.89	120.22 ± 7.65	0.128
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	80.98 ± 4.18	79.92 ± 3.15	0.248

*p value < 0.05 Significant, BMI: Body mass index, BP: Blood pressure, SD: Standard deviation

Table 2: Comparison of cardiovascular reflex test in patients of chronic PCOS and healthy controls

	PCOS (Mean \pm SD)	Healthy Controls (Mean \pm SD)	p Value
Delta HR (DBT)	13.23 ± 1.34	15.11 ± 1.19	0.000*
E:I ratio (DBT)	1.18 ± 0.49	1.31 ± 0.21	0.000*
Valsalva ratio	1.18 ± 0.78	1.42 ± 0.65	0.000*
30:15 ratio (LST)	1.19 ± 0.37	1.25 ± 0.22	0.000*
Rise in Heart rate (LST)	13.41 ± 3.71	8.55 ± 5.28	0.000*
Fall in SBP (LST) (mmHg)	11.85 ± 2.12	3.73 ± 4.84	0.000*
Delta DBP-Isometric handgrip test (mmHg)	10.22 ± 8.02	10.89 ± 7.94	0.087
CPT (mmHg)	9.31 ± 5.64	15.43 ± 4.01	0.000*

*p value < 0.05 Significant, LST- lying to standing, SBP- Systolic blood pressure, DBP- Diastolic blood pressure, CPT- Cold pressor test, SD: Standard deviation

Discussion

In patients with PCOS, we found a significant decrease in parasympathetic reactivity tests and sympathetic predominance. The E:I ratio dropped

statistically significantly in PCOS patients (1.19 ± 0.21). 1.21 is the ideal proportion. While numbers between 1.11 and 1.20 are seen as borderline, 1.10 is seen as aberrant. The E:I ratio and Δ HR values in the PCOS group were lower than in the control

group. There are many studies showing autonomic dysfunctions, as we found.

Cardiovascular reflex test and Heart rate variability are popular methods for evaluating cardiac autonomic function due to its simplicity and non-invasiveness. The cases had a significantly lower parasympathetic activity as compared to the age-matched controls. Saranya et al. obtained similar results, but there were no significant differences in other time-domain HRV parameters such as SDNN and rMSSD which is a measure of parasympathetic tone. [16] However, rMSSD, which represents parasympathetic HRV modulation, decreased in the cases studied. The findings presented here are consistent with those of Ji et al. (2018). [17] Yildirim et al. discovered that people with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) had a lower high frequency (HF) and a higher low frequency (LF) which signifies the parasympathetic tone as compared to the control group. [18] Our study found similar results, indicating that PCOS patients have increased sympathetic drive and decreased vagal tone (parasympathetic reactivity). However, it should be noted that some studies have yielded contradictory results. [19]

Previous cardiac autonomic functions studies on PCOS patients revealed increased sympathetic activity [20], which could be linked to hormonal and metabolic characteristics relevant to the syndrome's pathophysiology. Insulin resistance (IR) and hyperandrogenism (HA) are important hormonal abnormalities that contribute to the pathophysiology of PCOS, potentially leading to sympathetic dysfunction and chronic low-grade inflammation [5].

Two participants reported borderline and three abnormal values in the Valsalva ratio, 18 abnormal values in the E:I ratio, 10 borderline and nine abnormal values in the cold pressure test, and 6 borderline and 8 abnormal values in the hand grip test, among other cardiovascular reflex tests. Once more, this points to autonomic dysfunction in PCOS patients, which is consistent with Saranya et al.'s findings [12]. The same was also revealed by our findings.

The cardiac autonomic functions of women with PCOS were also assessed by Yildirim et al. [18], who discovered a decrease in the parasympathetic component and an increase in the sympathetic component. That study did find, however, that serum triglycerides had a high total cholesterol/HDL-C ratio and serum HDL-C levels were low. This can be another reason for autonomic dysfunction.

Over half of PCOS patients have obesity, which is a common finding in the condition [21]. In a study looking at the relationship between autonomic functions and cardiovascular risk factors in PCOS patients, it was hypothesized that the decrease in autonomic functions was related to weight gain

[22]. In addition to obesity, the PCOS group had higher rates of inflammation parameters, dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, and other cardiovascular risk factors. In a recent study, it was found that obese PCOS patients had significantly lower autonomic functions than the obese control group.

In the same study, however, no appreciable variations were found between non-obese PCOS patients and non-obese controls [23]. Though our subjects had normal BMI, these results, in conjunction with our research, indicate that obesity plays a significant part in the decline of cardiac autonomic functions in PCOS patients. Thus according to the findings of our research, PCOS patients have lower vagal tone (parasympathetic reactivity) and higher sympathetic drive.

Study's limitations: Some of our research's limitations include the small size of our study group. Larger-scale research is needed to validate these findings. Furthermore, no further biochemical or cardiac testing was carried out. Furthermore, the majority of research participants were younger, which might have impacted the study's findings. Further research with women in different age groups is required to validate the results.

Conclusions

Patients with PCOS exhibit increased sympathetic drive and decreased vagal tone, or parasympathetic reactivity. Since the ANS regulates cardiopulmonary functions, there is a chance that many therapeutic modalities will have adverse effects on the cardiovascular system. Finding ways to reduce these risks is of great interest. Our study used cardiovascular reflex test to evaluate cardiac autonomic function in PCOS patients, revealing early signs of dysfunction.

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